

Impact Objectives

- Support the EU Member States to establish a coherent and efficient regulatory framework
- Develop decision support tools for the European Aquaculture industry to foster improved regulatory decision-making

A toolbox for sustainable aquaculture

In response to growing impacts on the environment, Professor Trevor Telfer and Dr Lynne Falconer from the University of Stirling, alongside Dr David Jackson from Ireland's Marine Institute and Dr Hanne Kaas from DHI in Denmark, work together with a wider consortium to investigate solutions for creating a more sustainable future for European aquaculture

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What are some of the key challenges facing Europe's Aquaculture industry?

LF: Aquaculture is one of five sectors in the EU's Blue Growth Strategy considered to have high potential for sustainable jobs and growth, but in many European countries the lack of suitable sites is a major constraint to future expansion of the industry. Suitability of a location depends on many factors including biological requirements of the farmed species, environmental conditions, production technology and other legal, social and economic issues.

TT: Aquaculture development is supported by regulation and policy, however how it is implemented varies significantly between countries and production systems. The inconsistent regulatory and licensing frameworks throughout Europe is a challenge for the industry which gives undue differences in licensing conditions between European countries. In addition, these licensing conditions in the different countries are often inadequate and an important reason why aquaculture growth has been slower in Europe than other regions of the world. Stakeholders lack the necessary tools and information to decide on an issue, leading

to delays or uncertainty about a planning application or regulatory issues.

How are you evaluating environmental assessment and planning decision support tools?

TT: Existing assessment tools and those developed by TAPAS (Tools for Assessment and Planning of Aquaculture Sustainability) project are evaluated through consultation of the needs of stakeholders and regulators. This will help in the more efficient governance of aquaculture and alleviate bottlenecks in the licensing process. Essential tools are then tested at a number of case study locations and their use in developing policy within a number of country specific policy implementation case studies are assessed.

HK: Finally, the tools themselves or link to tools are incorporated into an overall decision support web-portal, the Aquaculture Sustainability Toolbox. This online toolbox disseminates knowledge on aquaculture and encompass decision support information, lessons learned from case studies and give access to tools such as models, monitoring technologies, data and guidance for aquaculture governance and licencing

throughout European Aquaculture.

Are the Aquaculture stakeholders supportive of this work?

DJ: We have found both the industry and regulators to be very supportive. Initial contacts made it clear that there was a certain amount of "questionnaire fatigue" however by using our personal contact networks and by direct approaches to groups and individuals we have built up a solid base of contacts, both individuals and organisations, with whom we maintain regular communications.

How will you make sure that the production environments and technologies are all incorporated into the Toolbox?

DJ: During the project development phase, one of the key priorities was to ensure the project covered the main production environments and technologies that are used in Europe. Consequently, a series of representative case study sites were selected for each of the different systems. These case studies also cover the main farmed species including salmon, trout, sea bass, sea bream, carp, oysters and mussels.

HK: The case study sites are used for the evaluation, development and validation of the tools, which include governance approaches, models and monitoring technologies. As the case study sites are representative of the systems and species used throughout Europe, the lessons learned and the encompassed tools can be easily applied elsewhere in Europe for similar systems. ►

Tools for management and growth of aquaculture

TAPAS responds to the challenges of sustainable aquaculture by combining both existing and new tools to improve the uses of environmental services by aquaculture in Europe, ultimately supporting its growth

In a changing world, with increasing populations, food security and the impact of food production on the environment is becoming a growing issue. One of the major and developing food production areas is aquaculture. Aquaculture has the potential to fill the gap in the supply of seafood, but also has the risk of being unsustainable and therefore cannot be established everywhere.

Through using an ecosystem approach, the EU's Horizon 2020 €7 million TAPAS (Tools for Assessment and Planning of Aquaculture Sustainability) project aims to build the sustainability of the EU's aquaculture industry. Project coordinator Professor Trevor Telfer and Dr Lynne Falconer, who are both based at the University of Stirling, Scotland, Dr David Jackson, from Ireland's Marine Institute, and Dr Hanne Kaas from DHI in Denmark work together with a wider consortium to produce the tools that are called for in order to build a sustainable aquaculture sector throughout Europe.

The project consortium consists of 15 partners from a variety of organisations from 11 countries across Europe. 'This breadth of expertise ensures that the outcomes of TAPAS and, in particular the Aquaculture Sustainability Toolbox, will be appropriate to the whole range of end-users encompassing all relevant stakeholder groups,' highlights Jackson. 'In particular, inclusion of regulators and industry accreditors as partners will ensure it is

credible for end-users for both regulation and sustainability accreditation.'

TAPAS is a four-year project, which started in March 2016, and is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 research programme. This project helps to prepare new strategies for the projected 25 per cent growth in sustainable aquaculture in Europe by 2020. 'TAPAS is evaluating existing aquaculture regulatory practices and the methods, tools and technologies used for implementation, to identify gaps, needs and bottlenecks and propose improved approaches,' outlines Telfer.

TAPAS aims to evaluate existing tools and models to identify the most appropriate methods and then, where necessary, suggest new or improved approaches. Jackson notes that after two years working on this project and undertaking the requirements analysis and extensive reviews, the 'most promising tools and models have been identified' and these are now being evaluated and developed. 'The modelling is supported by fieldwork, monitoring campaigns and earth observation products,' he says. TAPAS is implemented through a series of parallel and tightly integrated work packages and uses case studies throughout Europe to investigate, test and validate approaches. 'The overall objective is to establish a comprehensive 'toolbox' to support transparent and efficient licensing that will enhance environment sustainability, aquatic food security and blue growth', adds Kaas.

TOOL DEVELOPMENT

One of the TAPAS team's first priorities has been to evaluate the existing regulatory and licensing frameworks across Europe to identify potential bottlenecks and issues that affect sustainable development of the aquaculture sector. 'This established a solid knowledge base of the issues facing the sector with regards to regulation and licensing,' describes Telfer. 'Following on from this, and working in close collaboration with industry, regulators and certifiers, new and flexible approaches to

licensing are being developed which should be timelier and more cost efficient.'

'In Europe, and elsewhere across the world, many of the negative issues associated with aquaculture have been a result of poor planning and insufficient consideration of the environmental and socio-economic consequences of installing an aquaculture system in a location, affecting the sustainability and viability of farms,' adds Falconer. She points out that site selection and carrying capacity are therefore among the most important issues for the success of European aquaculture and 'predicate the need for sustainability, resilience and best practice guidelines, such as those provided by the Ecosystem Approach to Aquaculture'. Tools facilitating these types of analyses for preparation of applications for production licenses are cornerstones of the project.

Currently there is a need to bring together present and new ideas in aquaculture management that can be used over a range of locations throughout the EU. 'There is a clear need to focus on improving existing and/or developing new integrated operational tools for environmental impact assessment of aquaculture production, in line with the requirements for the allocation of licenses for aquaculture,' outlines Jackson.

The way these tools will work is to improve the approach to aquaculture licensing and to provide tools for decision support. The TAPAS tools will be designed to be cost effective and improve the environmental sustainability of aquaculture practices. 'The framework will include forecasting and modelling tools that can support and inform decision support systems, *in situ* observation technologies and early sensing and alarm systems,' adds Kaas.

'For aquaculture producers and regulators to implement the new approaches and tools, there will also need to be data collection and monitoring, so TAPAS is evaluating and developing new *in-situ* real time surveillance technologies,' says Falconer. These include autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV)

TAPAS looks at a range of cultured species, including mussels

technology for environmental inspection of aquaculture sites and optical sensors for automatic observations of water quality. 'Additionally, cost-efficient approaches which use Earth observation data, particularly the Sentinel satellites from the EC and European Space Agency's Copernicus programme are being developed for aquaculture planning and management,' she continues.

PAN-EUROPEAN SOLUTIONS

An issue in current aquaculture management practices is that regulatory and licensing frameworks across the EU are inconsistent and implementation of regulation and policy varies significantly across countries. These issues slow down growth of the industry and unnecessarily complicates development and progression. 'Often the necessary tools and information to assess the risks associated with aquaculture development are not available in an understandable form,' notes Telfer. 'There also needs to be more information and communication about many of the regulatory and licencing decisions, to improve transparency of the process and improve public understanding of how the industry is governed.'

'The shortfalls and inconsistencies in licensing processes throughout Europe also influence the chances of achieving the projected 25 per cent growth in sustainable aquaculture in Europe,' adds Kaas. 'Inconsistencies in licensing processes and access to useful tools and guidance leads to uneven competition and obstruct the growth potential of European sustainable aquaculture,' she continues. The pan-European perspective is therefore a consistent theme throughout the project.

To critically evaluate approaches, technologies and modelling tools for the range of different types of aquaculture sectors throughout the EU, the TAPAS team have employed a number of case studies located throughout Europe, investigating marine and freshwater environments. They are also based around different types of aquaculture production

systems from intensive marine cage and freshwater pond systems to extensive low feed pond systems. 'This range allows tools for all types of European aquaculture to be developed, tested and validated, using existing and newly developed models for environmental management,' observes Falconer. The methods developed can be evaluated in the case studies across the range of aquaculture sectors to strengthen the outcomes. 'In addition, there are case studies which are country specific and based on developing and implementation of aquaculture policy and governance for sustainable development,' she says. For example, the case study in Ireland is still in its early phase, but the outputs from TAPAS have already been able to make an important contribution to Ireland's review of the Aquaculture Licensing Process.

OUTREACH

Outreach and connections are an important way to share information gathered for the success of the project. Through their personal networks, different aspects of their work and direct approach through TAPAS the team has secured direct links with key stakeholders, including the Aquaculture Advisory Council (AAC), European Aquaculture Technology & Innovation Platform EATiP, Federation of European Aquaculture Producers (FEAP), national producer organisations and DGs, including Research and Mare. 'TAPAS partners regularly attend and present at national and international conferences for both academic and industry audiences and several journal articles have already been published,' says Telfer.

The oceans, seas and living aquatic resources can provide a significant contribution to food, energy and bio-based products. The focus for the future is to sustainably manage these resources to maximise benefits from Europe's oceans, seas and inland waters. TAPAS responds to these needs to develop management strategies for sustainable growth. ●

Project Insights

FUNDING

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 678396.

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- University of Stirling – Coordinator (UK)
- AquaBioTech Group (Malta)
- Aquaculture Stewardship Council
- DHI Water & Environment (Denmark)
- IMDEA Water Foundation (Spain)
- Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (Greece)
- Marine Institute (Ireland)
- Network of Aquaculture in Central and Eastern Europe (Hungary)
- Norwegian Institute for Water Research (Norway)
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